

Practical Idealistic Philosophy Of Exchange Assumption (A Comparative Study)

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 04, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: November 07, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Idealistic Philosophy, Legislator Formulates, Commercial Papers</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5652293</p>	<p><i>The Exchange assumption is one of the drafting methods used by the legislator in drafting some texts related to commercial papers, and this method involves creating a legal rule that organizes, complements, or explains what is missing or ambiguous in the contents of the paper, and certainly when the legislator formulates legal rules, it aims to achieve certain goals. They may be drafting and they may be practical, and the practical goals are divided into technical goals that become clear within the framework of a single commercial transaction, such as enhancing the speed of circulation or strengthening credit in the paper or the economy in invalidity (reducing cases of invalidity). But if we look closely at these ends, we will find that they aim to achieve other long-term goals that can constitute ideal ends for the morphological assumption. Perhaps the two most prominent ideas that we can put forward as an ideal end for it are the idea of the supposed will of the people of the morphological paper and the idea of transaction stability; It is as if the legislator, when supposed to organize, complete or explain the morphological behavior, is trying to rely on the supposed will of the people of the paper; They are the ones who created the morphological commitment to their will, and this will is the highest value that the legislator must track, or it is possible that he made these assumptions in order to maintain the stability of transactions, and to take note of these two goals we will divide this research into two demands, we deal in the first requirement to rely on the will as an ideal goal For the morphological assumption, and then we show in the second requirement the stability of transactions as an ideal goal for the morphological assumption.</i></p>

Introduction

The will constitutes a supreme value in voluntary actions. Therefore, we find that the legislator in many places stipulated formality in order to draw a path through which this will passes and establishes commitment, so that the expressed will is an apparent will. It has their apparent will if it is lacking, and to take note of this idea, we will divide this requirement into two branches. In the first section, we first deal with the concept of the assumed will of the people of the morphological paper, and then we show in the second section the evaluation of the assumed will as an ideal goal for the morphological assumption.

First branch

The concept of the assumed will of the people of the morphological paper

The morphological assumption contributes to building the morphological paper by filling the void left by the will of the people who liberated it. Therefore, the paper, according to the given given above, consists of a written will and an assumed one ;The legislator often sets complementary provisions that complement the will of the persons who make up the act ;People may lose sight of some issues ;These issues are complemented by the assumption of the will of the persons to act. ⁽¹⁾

This will is reached either by the legislator or the judge , ⁽²⁾ for example, in order for the judge to reach the supposed will of the parties, he must put himself in the place of the contracting parties so that he replaces them, so he goes back to the time of concluding the act, and puts himself in their circumstance and then anticipates the solution that he thinks they will take, and then he assumes that this is the solution , which tended to him the will of the people of trainers to act. ⁽³⁾

These complementary provisions, whatever their source - the legislator or the judge - are added to the expression of the will to complete what the persons who made up the act had to utter ;Some may neglect to organize some detailed issues because they did not appear in their minds, given that organizing any contract and taking note of its details requires a certain degree of legal knowledge that may not be available to some people, and in general, the will of the people who make up the act must dominate the organization of all issues Whether it is related to its creation or the arrangement of its effects, and a will outside the will of persons cannot regulate

any aspect of it, and hence the complement of the incomplete action must remain within the framework of the will that constitutes it⁽¹⁴⁾.

So assumptions must be made to conform to this will ;This will is the basis for the formation of the disposition, so some see that the completion of the deficient disposition is nothing but a process of interpretation of this disposition. will is the will of the truth or supposed, texts complementary reflect the assumed will of the people to act, and that the judge when interpreted to act first starts will to express to people and then looking for implicit their wills after that, did not find a solution to the question of resort to the supposed their will and called this trend (theoretical subjective (in complement disposition ⁽¹⁵⁾ (

Sometimes the expression of the will is in an explicit written way, and the other is assumed, which is inferred from their silence about the regulation of some issues ;So that this silence can only be interpreted as an acceptance that the complementary provisions fill the void that is silent about, and these provisions are by their nature an expression of the will of the persons who constituted the disposition ;On the grounds that there is an apparent will to be considered and an assumed will whose place is to take the complementary texts stipulated by the law, and the way of expressing this will is the silence of the two parties about stipulating what contradicts it. ⁽¹⁶⁾

Some distinguish between the presumed will and the implicit will ;In his view, the presumed will is made by the judge under his discretion ;The judge is the one who assumes it by creating the supposed solution that he expects from the conditions of the contract. As for the implicit will, it is implicitly disclosed by its owners by an indirect means that people are unfamiliar with in their dealings. ⁽¹⁷⁾

It is taken from this distinction that the presumed will may have been created by the legislator, not just the judge, ⁽¹⁸⁾ in many cases the legislator builds his assumptions on what he thinks represents the assumed will of people according to an abstract model, taking into account the common majority of things. frank did not express the way that they can choose through implicit expression by taking a certain position understood that they expressed their will implicitly, it is not possible, put the legislator himself or the judge in the circumstances of the contract and trying to reach the presumed will of the people, ⁽¹⁹⁾ in addition to the fact that the existence of the implicit will precedes the issue, while the existence of the assumed will is subsequent to it, ⁽¹⁰⁾ and we believe that there is no room to talk about the implicit will within the framework of morphological actions as it is governed by formality ;There is no room for implicit expression, but in the context of morphological dealing, we are only in front of an explicit will and an assumed will .

In order to clarify the idea of the assumed will as an ideal end of the morphological proposition, we give the following example:-

If we assume that a person creates a commercial remittance, so that he completes the mandatory data with the exception of the place of creation, the commercial remittance in the foregoing hypothesis is created through an explicit will that represents the written data and a hypothetical will that represents the will of the same persons ;When the legislator assumes that the place of the drawer is the place in which the commercial transfer was established, he places himself in the position of the drawer and in the same circumstances of creating the transfer, and therefore it is assumed that the drawer's will was directed to making his domicile a place for the creation of the transfer, since the nature of things outweighs this hypothesis ,so the legislator counts On this will and builds his assumption on it, the principle is that the people of the morphological paper are the ones who undertake the process of organizing it, and in general, the parties to any voluntary act are the ones who undertake the process of organizing it. or undone - all - must be in the light of the will, the inability of the parties to complete the disposition of the relationship and resorted to the judiciary, the judiciary shall act in the light of the completion of the assumed will of the parties, ⁽¹¹⁾ if the judge has a discretionary power to trace the supposed will of the parties, then the judge is the originator of this will, and if the judge does not have any discretionary power, but is governed by assumptions made by the legislator, in this case the legislator is the expresser of the supposed will of the parties, and Completion of the contract is defined as a means of remedying the deficiency in the content of the contract ;This is achieved by adding some obligations to the original content to organize the detailed issues left by the two contracting parties so that the result is consistent with good faith and what is required by honesty in dealing, ⁽¹²⁾ therefore it becomes clear that the completion of the contract represents an idea that arises when there is a need to do so, that the disposition is not complete, so there is no room for the completion of an act that has been completed and completed by its parties, ⁽¹³⁾ (and if there is a need, the supplementation must be within the framework of the presumed will of the persons to act.

From all of the foregoing, it is clear that the morphological paper, if its formal structure is not integrated ;If some of its statements were not organized or the statement was not written complete or written in an ambiguous manner, then it is organized, completed and interpreted according to the morphological assumption that the legislator makes by tracing through it the assumed will of the people of the morphological paper ? .This is what we will show in the next paragraph.

Second: - Evaluating the assumed will of the people of the paper as an ideal end for the morphological assumption

The idea of relying on the supposed will of the people of the morphological paper may seem acceptable - at first sight - as an ideal end for the morphological assumption, especially with the approach we made between the idea of completing the paper by means of the morphological assumption and the idea of completing the contract according to the ideas mentioned above.

But on the other hand, there are those who argue that completing the missing behavior is not by relying on the supposed will of the people who make it up ;And be complete but the shortage according to objective criteria away from the will of the parties ,and called on the supporters of this trend (objective theory) to complement the disposition of incomplete. ⁽¹⁴⁾)

The objective, complementary rules of conduct do not express the assumed will of the persons of the imperfect behavior, and to say the opposite is an assumption that has no basis in reality ;As the complementary rules and the provisions that they contain represent a direct expression of the will of the legislator and have nothing to do with the will of the persons formed to act upon them ;It rises when there is no direct expression issued by the contracting party, and hence the reason for completing the incomplete disposition is to fill the deficiency contained in the regulation of the disposition, and this completion takes place far from following the will of the contracting parties ;Therefore, the supplementation is the result of the will of the legislator, not the parties , ⁽¹⁵⁾ and in the same sense, another aspect of jurisprudence indicates that the completion of the incomplete act represents a legal process based on objective criteria that are abstract from the will of the persons who make up the act. These rules do not seek to define their presumed will ;Rather, it seeks to determine what can be inferred from the conduct from an objective point of view , ⁽¹⁶⁾ and according to the aforementioned idea, the completion of the missing morphological paper is not through assumptions that the legislator builds on the temporary will of persons, but rather based on objective considerations abstracted from persons.

Also, to say that the silence of the parties regarding the left issue of the disposition is an expression of the parties' consent to the complementary provisions, and therefore it expresses their will, is a statement that is answered that silence is an exceptional way to express the will that can only be taken in certain places proven contrary to the original, it is not permissible to extend ruling for other situations outside this exception , ⁽¹⁷⁾ and even in the context of the general rules dealing with silence as an exceptional expression, they did not always give it the rule of acceptance ;Sometimes it considers it an acceptance, sometimes a rejection, and at other times it considers it deception , ⁽¹⁸⁾ and if we accept for the sake of argument that the silence of the people of the morphological paper is an acceptance of the complementary morphological proposition rules, then this is a dependence on the will of the people over the will of the legislator and not the other way around.

Therefore, the completion of the morphological paper through the morphological assumption is not according to the will of the people of the paper, but rather according to the will of the legislator. on financial transactions within the framework of the general rules of civil law as a general asset ;One of the priorities of the commercial law in force is to limit the principle of the authority of the will and to give priority to the legal relationship over the contractual relationship ; ⁽¹⁹⁾ Therefore, we see that the legislator, while regulating, complementing, or explaining what was not regulated, missing or ambiguous in the contents of the paper, using the morphological assumption as a means to achieve this, did not intend to rely on the assumed will of the people of the morphological paper.

In addition to the above, there is another important matter that calls us to say this .If the legislator wanted to rely on the will of the people of the morphological paper, he would formulate the texts stipulating the propositions in the form of presumption, not in the form of objective and irrefutable rules ;Because the evidence, according to its nature, is refutable and the opposite is proven - as previously mentioned - if what you suppose does not correspond to the will of the people of the paper, it is possible to prove what is compatible with the will of the persons ;And thus refutes the assumption in order to conform to the will, and this matter is unimaginable for the texts prescribed for the morphological assumption as we went through earlier .

If we assume that a commercial draft has been drawn up and the place of payment is not mentioned in it, then according to the morphological assumption, the place of its creation is the address next to the name of the drawee ;This assumption, as we have seen, is based on the most likely possibility that the nature of things makes more likely ;However, this possibility does not reach the level of certainty in any way. The presumed will of the people of the paper may not intend that the subject of its payment is the address of the drawee ;If the legislator wanted to trace this will, he would formulate the hypothesis in the form of a morphological presumption, so that if what he assumed did not correspond to the will of the persons, it would be possible to prove the other hypothesis that corresponds to the will of the persons, and then the presumption falls and depends on what corresponds to their will, but he - the legislator - did not do that. He formulated morphological propositions with objective rules, regardless of the extent to which they correspond to the will of the assumed persons.

From all of the above, it seems clear that the idea of relying on the assumed will of the people of the morphological paper was not the goal of the ideal morphological assumption ;The legislator, while formulating these assumptions, does not think about the extent of the applicability of what he assumed to the will of the

people of the supposed morphological paper, as there may be other ideal goals that are more important to which he seeks.

The second requirement

Transaction stability as an ideal end of morphological assumption

In general, the legislator seeks to ensure the stability of transactions. This end is not limited to a specific legal field without another, but rather it is a goal that pervades all laws regulating financial transactions, whether commercial or civil ;However, the concept of transaction stability as a legal end may differ within the framework of the general rules when transactions are stable in the commercial environment, which requires a statement of the concept of transaction stability as an ideal end for the morphological assumption, which we will show in the first section and then show in the second section the evaluation of the stability of transactions as an ideal end for the assumption Morphological.

First branch

The concept of transaction stability as an ideal end of the morphological assumption

The subject of the stability of transactions of important issues within the framework of legal studies so that flattens the scope of the topic on all branches of law, often looking the idea of the stability of the transaction as a very important of the goals that the law seeks to achieve , but he often has offered to achieve justice. ⁽¹²⁰⁾

Every lawmaker in different countries aims through years of legislation to achieve several goals at the forefront of those goals reflected the stability of transactions as an end sought by the legislator brilliantly as well as justice and social progress. ⁽¹²¹⁾

The idea of the stability of transactions has been defined as “the stability of the effects of human facts in money through their permeation and dissolution , ⁽¹²²⁾ “and it is taken from this definition that the idea of stability of transactions is closer to legal actions than human facts - although stability in the effects of facts is also required - but the stability desired in the advanced definition concerns transactions, an expression that leads in its significance ⁽¹²³⁾ To the meaning of actions such as selling and the like. ⁽¹²⁴⁾

Likewise, the purpose of the stability of transactions is not only related to the enforcement and dissolution of transactions ; Rather, it is required even when it is established. In many cases, as the legislator has passed by, the legislator completes the incomplete behavior, so it is complete and stabilizes when it is established, and then settles when it becomes effective and dissolved .

And we believe that it is very difficult to give a comprehensive and definitive definition of the stability of transactions as an idea that extends to all branches of law, given that the stability of transactions within the framework of civil law as an end differs from the stability of transactions within the framework of commercial law, and to this meaning refers to German jurisprudence considering that the idea of stability Transactions are among the fruits of the theory of the declaration of will ,which is of German origin and has been influenced by French jurisprudence by taking into account the tangible phenomenon that the transaction trusted by adopting the idea of declaration alone, as it had a role in calming the souls of the dealers through the confidence it generates that they were not surprised by those who wanted Contrary to what seemed to them that appearance , ⁽¹²⁵⁾) but this theory is in violation of the general rules for the transfer and protection of rights ;As these rules, as is well known, do not purify defenses, and therefore a person of good faith may be surprised by defenses that did not appear to him at first sight.

Therefore, German jurists saw that the purpose of the stability of transactions within the framework of general rules is not appropriate to the speed in the transfer of rights and the protection required for them in the commercial environment. Therefore, they began to differentiate between two types of stability, namely (stability of rights) and (stability of dealings) , ⁽¹²⁶⁾ and this idea and its divisions were received by Professor (Demoge) in order to formulate from it his idea of the stability of dealing .

It has divided the stability of transactions into two types ;The first was called (static stability) and the second was called (kinetic stability). As for static stability - the stability of rights - it requires that a person does not lose his right against his will ;Remaining rights under the authority of their owners is a desire that society cannot abandon, and this means that any act of the right made by those who did not possess that authority against the owner of the original right should not be taken into account. The right has good faith, and this achieves individual security represented by the protection of the right. ⁽¹²⁷⁾ .

However, social life needs for its development and sustainability at the same time the activity and movement necessary for this development, which is based on expanding opportunities and rates of production and exchange, and in general expanding dealings, whether economic or social , ⁽¹²⁸⁾ the growth and flowering of this transaction requires legal means to encourage it, and this may not be achieved through complete bowing to the will that constitutes the act and making it sacred, and steadfastness on its effects absolutely ; ⁽¹²⁹⁾ If the movement (handling and exchange) are required for the development of society, the stability of the results is required Castaqra presence is in itself, and that he called stability (Damuj) motor stability , which it considers necessary to achieve safety and social protection reassuring goal dealing and its sustainability and development . ⁽¹³⁰⁾

In many cases, this type of stability and its predecessor - static stability - are at a crossroads, which necessitates harmonizing them or giving priority to one over the other if necessary. So that dealing and exchange is only encouraged where this encouragement is appropriate through the protection of trust that increases the demand for dealing; And that is by giving preference to the interest of the transaction when the real center is hidden behind an apparent situation and the others delude that it is real, and that illusion is not due to his mistake and negligence, and when the third party is well-intentioned. ⁽¹³¹⁾

Perhaps the most prominent evidence for the idea of kinetic stability is represented in the rule of purification from defenses that protect the bearer of good faith from defenses that may not be apparent to him and thus encourage exchange - endorsement - and protect its outputs, and the matter is different under the general rules given that the idea of transfer of right does not include The purification of defenses and thus is a testament to static stability, and in this example the difference between the idea of the stability of transactions in the commercial environment and those known in the civil law is evident.

Some criticize the idea of kinetic stability in terms of being based on economic considerations rather than legal considerations, in addition to that it tries to protect exchange and the speed of economic activity and considers that achieving this constitutes a unique goal so that even those who have bad faith can benefit from it. ⁽¹³²⁾

Therefore, some see that the idea of kinetic stability is valid as an end in the field of commercial law only, and is not valid in the field of other laws. ⁽¹³³⁾ Trade, according to some, is like a plant that thrives in a climate of speed and within the soil of stability. ⁽¹³⁴⁾

From all of the above, we can know the stability of transactions as a unique goal that the legislator seeks to achieve through multiple means through which he ensures the stability of legal actions when establishing, implementing and fulfilling them.

In the light of the advanced concept, the stability of transactions should not be confused with some legal ideas that may be mixed with them, and among the concepts that are close in meaning to the stability of transactions is the theory of the apparent situation, which represents an incorrect realistic situation hidden under a seemingly correct legal form. ⁽¹³⁵⁾

The two ideas are similar in terms of their wisdom. The wisdom of the apparent situation theory is represented in declaring the enforcement of the legal actions issued by the owner of the apparent situation, even if his actions were not based on legal authority, in order to achieve social security and the public interest, as well as the case for the wisdom of the stability of financial transactions represented in imparting stability on legal acts, ⁽¹³⁶⁾ and in this a significant contribution to achieving social safety.

As for the difference between them, it is that maintaining the apparent situation may contribute to the stability of transactions, meaning that their relationship represents the relationship of the end to the means, so that maintaining the apparent situation is one of the means of stabilizing transactions.

The legislator, while looking forward to the stability of transactions, has tools; Many of them, for example, are formal. They aim to achieve a general goal of instilling confidence in people, and then providing stability in transactions and achieving legal security, ⁽¹³⁷⁾ and the general goal is achieved by achieving several sub-goals that the formality seeks to achieve; As protecting the interests of the parties, it is a means to ensure the parties' satisfaction and protects the will from falling into error by drawing the path that the will must take, as well as the formality aims to protect others by providing them with a measure of information so that they can be aware of the details of the legal actions that it is located between the parties, so it prevents fraud as well as contributing to the clarity of these behaviors in front of not only others but even public authorities, and all of this in turn leads to the legal security and stability that the legislator seeks, ⁽¹³⁸⁾ and it is known that the morphological interaction is governed by formality, and as we have seen, the formality that makes up the morphological paper is divided into written formality and assumed formality, and the latter is assumed through clear objective rules that do not accept proof of the opposite and formalism, as we have seen, contributes greatly to Ensuring the stability of transactions, whether this formality is written or assumed, and in light of all of the above, we can know the stability of transactions in the light of the idea of kinetic stability as an ideal end for the morphological assumption as (that is the end that the morphological assumption seeks to achieve by ensuring the stability of morphological behaviors when they are established by organizing them or completion or interpretation, protection and acceleration of circulation and fulfillment), was this end the goal of the ideal morphological hypothesis. ?

second branch

Evaluating the stability of transactions as an ideal end of the morphological assumption

The idea of the stability of the transactions seem more acceptable than others as an end ideal for assuming Morphological, especially if we look at the legal texts prescribed for these assumptions as part of the system of trade law, the law, which trade is an economic activity must be based on trust, honesty and abide by the rules of law, ⁽¹³⁹⁾ the availability of the advanced considerations aims to perpetuate this activity, and this is nothing but a guarantee of the dynamic stability of transactions.

The morphological transaction, as is the case with the rest of the aspects of commercial activity, is governed by these considerations. It must be practiced on the basis of trust, honesty and strict adherence to the rules of the law. Therefore, we see it imposing penalties when the advanced considerations fail to reach the limit of disrupting the kinetic stability and weighting the static stability ;For example, when the legal holder is not in good faith, he cannot take refuge in the rule of purification from defenses, and if we studied the sections of the morphological assumption, we would find that it seeks an ideal and unique goal, which is to ensure the kinetic stability of the morphological interaction ;That is, the permanence of this activity and the encouragement of demand for it. The applications of the organized morphological assumption reduce the cases of invalidity as we have experienced, and thus keep the morphological paper alive and able to circulate ;And thus contribute to ensuring kinetic stability to deal Morphological it is assumed the data were not included in the morphological paper, which forgave the law assumed , which thus plays an important role in the establishment Morphological commitment and ensure stability so we see that the Fiqh is required in writing special with evidence paper to be fixed and serious ⁽¹⁴⁰⁾ to ensure the stability of dealing, and this is with regard to the written formality.

As for the assumed formality through the morphological assumption, we are not exaggerating if we say that its stability is more powerful than the stability of written formalism ;It is established by explicit legal texts formulated in the form of substantive rules that do not accept refutation or proof of the contrary and by assumption ,they are not present on the paper, and therefore will not be subject to erasure or distortion other than the written formality that is subject to this, and it is not only to ensure the stability of the data when it is created Even when deliberating, we find that there are morphological assumptions that contribute to strengthening this characteristic of the paper, thus removing all ambiguities that taint the authority of the holder in endorsing the paper ;Like the proposition of the promissory note, where this characteristic is assumed when the paper does not include this trait, and there is no crime that the purpose of this ideal assumption is to ensure kinetic stability through the possibility of transmission and circulation of the morphological paper by endorsement, which increases the volume of circulation, and the same applies to the applications of the assumption The complementary morphemes, they all complement the incomplete morphological behavior, which leads to the removal of all ambiguity in the morphological behavior, and we saw that these assumptions lead to the strengthening of credit as well, and certainly this encourages the demand for morphological dealing and thus ensures kinetic stability, and the same applies to the interpreted morphological assumption Among these applications is what effectively contributes to raising the conflict between the contents of the morphological paper, which increases the clarity of the content of the statement and contributes to ensuring the stability of the morphological interaction, so it can be rightly said that the idea of the stability of the morphological interaction represents the ideal goal of the morphological assumption, and we see that the morphological assumption has tended towards the kinetic stability that ensures the permanence of the morphological deal ;By increasing the turnout for it and ensuring its continuity through circulation more than its tendency towards the idea of static stability, and perhaps a question that can be posed in this regard is to the effect, if we say that ensuring the stability of kinetic interaction represents the goal of the ideal morphological assumption, which leads as a result to an increase in demand for morphological dealing In order to provide the elements of kinetic stability such as stability and speed in circulation and the strength of credit, why not say that the ideal morphological assumption is to ensure the demand for morphological dealings . ?

In fact, we see that increasing the demand for exchange transactions constitutes an economic goal rather than a legal one .It contributes to reducing the effects of inflation, given that a single currency note can replace a large cash block ;This has positive effects on the economy, and this matter does not constitute a philosophical goal for the science of law, but rather a purely economic goal.

Therefore, it can be rightly said that the ideal goal of the morphological assumption is to ensure the stability of the morphological transaction, and specifically the kinetic stability of this transaction, which means ensuring the permanence of the morphological transaction through the clarity and stability of the rights established in the morphological paper and the stability of the consequences of its transmission, guarantee and fulfillment ;Ensuring this means achieving an ideal goal, which is to ensure the kinetic stability of the morphological transaction.

Conclusion

At the conclusion of our research on the topic of the ideal practical philosophy of the morphological assumption, we reached a number of results and two proposals that we present in turn:

First, the results:

- 1The morphological assumption is one of the moral formulation methods used by the legislator with the intention of organizing, completing or interpreting the contents of the morphological paper that the people of the paper may neglect or neglect to write in an optimal way .
- 2The formality in the framework of morphological papers in most cases is divided into two parts ;The first is the written formality that people emptied the paper, and the second is the assumed formality

organized by the legislator with the intention of completing the deficiency in the written formality or removing the ambiguity of some of its contents if it is written in an ambiguous manner.

- 3 There are practical short-term goals that the morphological legislator sought to achieve through the morphological assumption, such as enhancing the speed of circulation of the paper by assuming the promissory note in the event that it is not mentioned, as well as strengthening credit through the assumption of solidarity, as well as the economy in nullity through the assumptions of missing data, and then preventing Paper invalidation.
- 4 When the legislator organizes the statements that have not been organized or is supposed to complement them or remove the ambiguity resulting from the conflict of their data, he does not rely much on the will of the people of the supposed paper, but rather he formulated his assumptions with complete impartiality from them.
- 5 The idea of stability of transactions as a legal end within the framework of commercial behavior in general and morphological behavior in particular differs from the idea of stability of transactions within the framework of general rules ;While the general rules seek to ensure the stability of rights, the morphological legislator seeks to ensure the stability of dealing, and this idea is called the idea of kinetic stability, which represents ensuring the permanence of morphological activity and the stability of the consequences of the transfer of rights morphologically.
- 6 It turns out that the ideal practical goal that the morphological legislator seeks from the various morphological assumptions is to ensure the kinetic stability of the morphological transaction by ensuring the permanence of the morphological activity and the stability of the results resulting from the creation, circulation, guarantee, acceptance and fulfillment of morphological papers . The goal represents the ultimate goal of the legislator within the framework of the legal goals, although it may lead to an important economic result represented in reducing the state of inflation, but this last goal is not considered as an end within the science of law .

Second: Suggestions:

- 1 In line with the goal of kinetic stability, we suggest to the Iraqi legislator to amend the text of Article (45) of the Trade Law by adding a third paragraph that assumes the validity of the lowest written amounts in the case of multiple writing of the transfer amount several times in letters and several times in numbers, so that the text of the paragraph is as follows: (Third: If the transfer amount is written several times in letters and several times in numbers, it is assumed that the correct transfer amount is the least amount written in letters .
- 2 We suggest that the legislator adopt the provisions of the Unified American Trade Law when he assumed the validity of the handwritten data when it contradicts the printed data, and this is done by adding a fourth paragraph to the text of Article (45) of the Trade Law so that its text is as follows :) Fourth: If the paper includes printed data and other handwritten data, the priority is given when there is a conflict between them for the handwritten data, when the handwritten data is supported by the signature of the person who added the statement.(
- 3 The Iraqi Trade Law does not include an assumption that solves the problem of not specifying the type of currency in the paper despite the big problems that result from that , as well as if the currency is mentioned according to a joint designation between the country of creation and the country of fulfillment, so we suggest that the Iraqi legislator add an article that includes an assumption that solves the advanced problems that Its sequence follows Article (45) of the Trade Law and its text is as follows: (If the transfer amount is written without indicating the type of currency under which it was issued, or if the currency denomination is shared between the country of creation and the country of fulfillment, the following provisions shall apply :
 First: If the transfer was made in Iraq and is due for payment, and the type of currency was not specified when writing its amount, it is assumed that it was made in the Iraqi currency.
 Second: If the country of origin differs from the country of payment and the type of currency was not specified when writing the transfer amount ,it is assumed that it was drawn up according to the currency of the country of payment .
 Third: If only the denomination of the currency is mentioned and the denomination is shared between the country of payment and the country of origin, it is assumed that the transfer amount has been drawn up according to the currency of the country of payment.

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[9] - We must note that we do not care much about the existence of the implicit will of the people of the pure paper or not. Rather, what we are looking for is the extent to which the legislator relies on the supposed will of the persons or not.

[10] - Marwan Hussein Attia, The Implicit Will of the Original Constituent Authority , PhD thesis submitted to the College of Law, University of Karbala ,2020 , p.31 .

[11] -Dr .Abdel Fattah Hegazy, Interpretation of the Civil Contract, Institute of Arab Research and Studies, League of Arab States, Cairo, 1988, p. 110 p. 48.

[12] -Salam Abdul-Zahra Al-Fatlawi, Contract Scope, PhD thesis submitted to the College of Law, University of Baghdad, 2005, p. 31 .

[13] -Abdul-Mahdi Kazem Nasser, Economics in the termination of the contract, a doctoral thesis submitted to the Faculty of Law, University of Karbala, 2017, p. 30

[14] - Dr .Ismail Ghanem, The General Theory of Obligations, Sources of Obligation, Abdullah Wahb Library, Egypt, p. 96 .One of the supporters of this trend is also d .Wahid al-Din Sawarn, Expressing the will in Islamic jurisprudence, first edition, 1960, p. 323.

[15th] - Abdel Fattah Hegazy, the previous source, p. 125.

[16] -Dr .Jacques Ghassan, The Extended Civil Law, The Effects and Effects of the Contract, translated by Mansour Al-Qadi, University Foundation for Studies and Publishing, Beirut, 2001, pp. 80-81.

[17] - d . Abdel Fattah Hegazy , the previous source.124-123 ,

[18] - For example , we find that Article 81 of the Iraqi civil law , pointed to cases of silence clothes and is no longer a way to express their will only if Abesth conditions is inferred that it is acceptable , while we find that Article (340) in the second paragraph concerning the transfer of religion is considered Silence was refused when it stipulated ” :If the transferor or the assignee notifies the transfer to the transferee and sets a reasonable time for accepting the transfer, then the time has expired without the acceptance being issued, the silence of the transferee shall be considered as a rejection of the transfer “. Also, Article (2/121) considered the lack of statement) silence (as a form of deception when it stipulated - 2” It is considered deception to make a statement in trust contracts in which it is necessary to guard against suspicion of the statement, such as treason in Murabaha, guardianship and association “. Although the general rules consider silence a way Exception to express the will, not that you did not treat it - within the framework of the exception - as always accepting ;Therefore, it is not possible to withdraw the special exceptional provision that makes the silence of clothes an acceptance of the silence of the transfer persons about the organization of some data and the interpretation of their silence as acceptance of the rules of the morphological assumption .

[19] - paragraph stipulates (3) of Article) first (of the Trade Act in force as part of the basis of a statement on which this law .3” The reduction of the principle of authority and will give priority to the legal relationship to the contractual relationship ”.

[20] -Dr .Muhammad Jamal Attia Issa, Legal formalism, a comparative study between man-made systems and Islamic law, Dar Al-Nahda Al-Arabiya, Cairo, 1994, p. 22.

[21] - Ali Al-Khafeef , Provisions of Sharia Transactions , third edition , Arab Thought House , Kuwait , p.37 .

[22] - Ali Hamid Kazem Al Shukri , Stability of Financial Transactions , PhD thesis submitted to the College of Law, University of Karbala ,2014 , p.25 .

[23] - The single indication is an introduction to get to the meaning , there is no sequence between the meaning of the individual and significance , for more detail see , Mr .al - Khoei, the finest reports, the first part, search Naini, Mostafavi publications, Qom, Iran, 1368, p.13 .

[24] - d . Abdel Moneim Farag Al-Sada, The Origins of the Law , first edition , Al-Halabi Press , Egypt , ,1965pg.60 .

[25] -Dr .Adnan Ibrahim Al-Sarhan, Modern trends of responsibility for harmful act, a comparative critical study in the UAE and Qatari laws in light of the developments of responsibility in French law, research published in the Journal of Sharia and Law, issued by the College of Law, UAE University, Issue 71, Year 31, 2017 ,p. 144 .

[26] _ Academie de Droit International ,Recueil Des Cours - Collected Courses, martinusnijhoff publishers, boston 1991-II, p328.

See also in detail the idea of) stability of rights and stability of dealings (d . Abdel Basset al -Jmiei, the agency phenomenon , research published in the Journal of Legal and Economic Science , Ain Shams University , second edition .1963 , p.335 .

[27] - JaqusLeaute , Le Mandate apparent Dans Ses rapports aveo La Theoriegerenal l opparence, revue, trim estrilleAnnee, 1947, p302.

[28] -Henry Batefull, The Philosophy of Law, translated by Dr. Smouhi Extraordinary, University Thought Library, Oweidat Publications, Beirut, 1972 ,pg. 46.

[29] -Dr. Adnan Ibrahim Al-Sarhan, previous source, p. 145.

[30] - JaqusLeaute , op, cit , p303

[31] -Dr .Adnan Ibrahim Al-Sarhan, previous source, p. 145.

[32] -Dr .Abdel Rahman Eyada, The basis of the nodal commitment, general theory and applications, Alexandria, 1972 ,p.94 .

[33] -Mohamed Sherif Jamal, The Theory of the Apparent Situation and the Stability of Transactions ,Publications of the Faculty of Law and Political Science, AkliMohandOlhaj University - Bouira - 2019, p. 42.

[34] -Dr .Yassin bin Nasser Al-Khatib, The Theory of Transaction Stability and its Impact on Contracts, An Applied Study on Some Financial Transactions, Research published in Al-Adl Journal, Issue 63, Jumada Al-Awwal, 1435 AH, pg. 47.

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[36] - Ali Hamid Kazem Al Shukri, previous source, p. 64.

[37] . -Dr ..Muhammad Jamal Attia, the previous source, p. 196.

[38] -Dr .Salem Hammad Shaaban Al-Dahdouh, Formality in Civil Contracts in Jordanian Law ,A Comparative Study, Publications of the Faculty of Law, University of Jordan, 1989, p. 122 .

[39]Article (3) of the Iraqi Trade Law states, "Trade is an economic activity that must be based on trust, honesty and strict adherence to the rules of the law .We did not find anything corresponding to this article in the Egyptian Trade Law No. (17) of 1999, as well as the French Law of 1807 ,as well as the Unified American Trade Act, although it was known for good faith) good faith)having defined him in the paragraph(t)of item(2 (Subject) 1-201 (On that (GAM already follow reasonable commercial standards in fair dealing) (- 1-201 " (t) "Good faith", except as otherwise provided in article 5, means honesty in fact and the observance of reasonable commercial standards of fair dealing" (

[40] -Dr .Super Shamaa, d .Fawzi Muhammad Sami, Commercial Law, Commercial Papers, Legal Library, Baghdad, without a year of printing, p. 55 .

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